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A Pastoral Counselling Approach to the Challenges of Widowhood in Traditional Igbo Land

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Abstract

This research argued that women in traditional Igbo land are faced with myriads of factors challenging their personalities, worth, dignity and contributions towards development in the family and the larger society. One of the obnoxious cultural traits that dehumanizes, relegates and obliterates womanhood in traditional Igbo society is widowhood practices. This is the case in most African climes, where male chauvinism, oppression and women relegation are dominant features of their culture. While this practice is entrenched in the traditional culture of the Igbo people, the women are seen to be the ones encouraging and enforcing it against their folks in Igbo land in most cases. Descriptive phenomenology approach was adopted for this research; while secondary sources of data collection and analysis were equally employed to give the work the desired attention. It was discovered that widowhood practices in traditional Igbo land, subject women to various forms of sexual abuses, stigmatization, denials, poverty and incapacitation; and thus, reduces them to the status of slaves in the society. Women undergoing these treatments are psychologically, socially, religiously and economically unproductive and cannot contribute meaningfully to development. The research recommended that Christian religious leaders should rise to the occasion and bring this obnoxious widowhood practices in Igbo land to a stop. Pastoral counselling approaches of teaching, preaching, prayer and care should be engaged to assist widows and as means of discouraging cultures perpetuating this ugly practice. The work further advised that pastors should work with government agencies, women groups and NGOs in the area of advocacy and empowerment for widows suffering untold hardship in the hands of cultures that still uphold this menace.

Keywords: Widowhood, tradition, pastoral counselling, Igbo land, cultural practices

Introduction

Women have been for the most part made objects of discrimination and male dominance in various parts of Igbo land and elsewhere in the world. Hence, Lane (1985, p.664), opined that, "down through the ages, women have been regarded as second class citizens. They are stereotyped into roles of dependency, submission as passivity... exploited as objects... defined in terms of men... excluded from the centers of power and the decision-making processes in the society." Obi and Ogbenna (2010, p.328), averred that, in Africa, sex inequality is a strong belief and the majority of women are placed under severe socio-cultural and economic disabilities and discriminations in areas like: inheritance rights, childlessness and male child preference, exploitation, domestic violence, polygamy, sexual harassment and obnoxious widowhood practices. In fact, women have always been seen and treated as unequal in the whole of known and recorded history.

Widowhood practices is one of the many woes that has subjugated womanhood in traditional Igbo land. In this clime, men (widowers) are treated differently and are allowed some privileges at event of the demise of their wives; while the contrary is the case at the death of

the men's folk. As such a dehumanizing and traumatizing elements of widowhood rites are meted out on the woman whose husband is dead (Obi and Ogbenna, 2010). Speaking further on this, Uchem (2005, p.65), noted that, "a further socio-cultural face of gender inequality is manifested in the often talked about degrading treatments which are meted out against widows in some Nigerian cultures." The sad thing about these cultures where such treatments exist, is that the widow is generally suspected to have killed or caused the death of the husband directly or indirectly. Thus, she is meant to undergo certain dehumanizing rituals. All that is possible because as an "inferior" human being, it is automatically believed that the woman is the culprit (Uchem, 2005).

The research methodology adopted was descriptive phenomenology. This method according to Ituma (2015, p.37) is "an attempt at describing the diversity, complexity and richness of experience." This method enabled the researcher to uncover descriptively, the experiences widows undergo in Igbo land. Equally used were the secondary sources of data collection, where materials from the library and online contents were accessed to enrich the research with necessary information needed.

Analysis of Key Concepts

Agumagu (2007, p.16), averred that a widow is a woman who has lost her husband by death and has not remarried. Townsend (1995, p.891) states that, "a widow is a woman whose marriage partner is dead and who has not remarried." Nnachi and Nnubia (2011, pp.146-147) maintained that, "widowhood means the condition in which a woman finds herself at the death of her husband." Widowhood practices entail the traditional agonizing conditions widows are subjected to as their husbands die. Osita-Njoku and Uwaoma (2001), Kolo (2002) and Lannap (2005) expressed that widowhood is a period of grief and pain, marginalization of women, accompanied by emotional deprivation, forceful seizure of property and cultural seclusion.

On traditions, Isichei (1976, p.11), averred that, "people will not look forward to posterity who never look backward to their ancestors." Tradition is a part of culture that is passed from person to person or generation to generation. Ezekwugo (1992, p.231) said, "that every racial group of people in the world has a code of ordinances, mores and lores which are supposed to have decreed by the land. These sanctions are the traditions (*odinana*), ordinances, customs and bye-laws enshrined in the sinews and marrows of a social fabric of ancestral heritage."

On the other hand, pastoral care and counseling are valuable instruments by which the church stays relevant to human needs. They are ways of translating the good news into a language of relationships. Clinebell (1984), affirmed that:

Counselling can help save those areas of our lives that are shipwrecked in the storms of our daily living, broken on the hidden reefs of anxiety, guilt, and lack of integrity. An effective caring and counselling program, in which both minister and trained lay persons serve as enablers of healing and growth can transform the interpersonal climate of a congregation making a church, a place where wholeness is nurtured in persons throughout the life cycle (pp.13-14).

Widowhood Practices in Traditional Igbo Land

In traditional Igbo setting, the funeral rites of a dead man involve many ritual practices that are necessary for religious change. These rituals most times are very adverse to the wellbeing and existence of the widow of the dead man. Nmah (2003, p.70), accentuated that:

“widowhood practices in Igbo land are another area in which women are reduced to slave states.”

Ogu, Obi, Isidiho (2020, p. 1051), opined that:

Many communities still retain the notion that widows are responsible for the death of their husbands; therefore, to prove their innocence they are often compelled to undergo certain rituals. In this case, women whose husbands died undergo series of widowhood practices which have various implications.

Ndulue (1995, p.108), classified widowhood practices in Igbo culture into three main groups:

The first group is widows whose husbands took traditional titles before their death. The second group is widows whose husbands did not take any traditional title before their death. The third group involves some Igbo communities who do not believe in overt self-denial or mortification while mourning a deceased husband.

In the first two cases, there are similarities. But widowhood for women whose husbands took traditional title before their death is very stringent and primitive.

Widowhood generally, was considered a taboo in traditional Igbo land and as such, various practices were carried out against the woman in order to make her ritually clean, before integrating her back into the society (Nwankwo, 2014). Thus, such obnoxious widowhood practices include but not limited to the following:

Excommunication, restrictions and isolation of the widow: Nmah (2003, p.79), said that, “in parts of Igbo land, when a man dies, the wife is secluded. That is, she is kept in a separate place. Such a woman does not come out for about eight days after the death of her husband. She will not be touched by anybody in this secluded place.” She is meant to eat with stick not her hand. In those days she is not shaved for a long period of time. Sometimes, it will take years before her hair was shaved (Nwankwo, 2014).

Ezeaku (1990, p.107), noted that “as soon as the husband dies, a small make-shift hut is built for her at the back of her residential house. She is to an extent excommunicated from the people. She isolates from the people in her community. The hut is built with materials which could easily be discarded and cast into evil forest as soon as the burial and funeral ceremonies of the late husband were completed.

The widow is isolated and restricted from getting into the market to buy or sell. If she needs anything she has to look for someone to do that for her. This makes the situation of a widow who is childless, breastfeeding a baby or sick very deplorable as the law has no consideration. The widow cannot attend meetings or other social functions (Ogu, Obi, Isidiho, 2020).

Shaving of the widow's hair and wearing of sackcloth: Obi and Ogbenna (2010), identified another area of violence against women in Igbo land. This is in respect to widowhood practices. He affirmed that, “another area of violence is forced shaving of the widow's hair as a symbol of respect for the dead husband and to make her unattractive to other men while mourning. The widows look abandoned, hopeless, ugly, rejected and helpless” (p.335).

The beauty of a woman consists of the hairs on her head. Shaving of the hairs on the head and other parts of the body seems to be the ugly responsibility of the *umuokpu* or *umuada* (married daughters of the deceased family) or even the older widows. The widow is compulsively taken behind the kitchen, near a bush and given a clean shave by these women with ordinary razor blade despite the health risks (Ogu, Obi, Isidiho, 2020).

On sackcloth, Obi and Ogbenna (2010, p.335) furthermore said that, “the imposition of black mourning cloth makes mourning frightful and gloomy. It instills fear in the widow and

generated nightmares. It makes them look like outcasts and people avoid them as such." She must wear one particular mourning clothes for one year not even when it is totally worn out.

Drinking of the water used to wash the corpse of the deceased husband: Nmah (2003, p.79), observed that "there are extreme cases where the woman is forced to drink water used in washing her husband's corpse, especially, if she was accused of being responsible for the husband's death." Similar to this is the act of walking across the corpse by the widow as it lay on the floor to show that she has not killed the husband because everyone now sees her as a witch and call her bad names especially very young widows (Ogu, Obi, Isidiho, 2020).

Challenges of Widowhood in Traditional Igbo Land

The challenges of widowhood are enormous. It ranges from socio-cultural, economic and psychological dimensions. Widows pass through a lot of denials, abuse, stigmatization and other forms of violence in the face of cultures and traditions entrenching this practice.

Socio-cultural challenges: Widowhood practice is shrouded in superstitions that subject the victims to fear both from the kinsmen of her husband and the fear of being harmed by the spirit of her dead husband. The women are not accorded full social recognition in accord to the dignity of their person. According to Obi (2001, p.109) "the widow becomes aware of her limitations since the source of her pride has passed away." The children could be subjected to social ridicule and torture since they lack protection. It brings untold hardship, distress, and cries in the family.

Economic challenges: Widows are at risks of economic deprivation, especially the younger ones. In a culture where the men are seen as the breadwinners, in the event of death, their widows are exposed to a greater danger of economic hardship and hunger. The widows must live in their husband's family no matter the situation because re-marriage is usually difficult. Therefore, widowhood remains an easy transition to economic poverty as the widow is faced with loss of status and resources (Ogu, Obi, Isidiho, 2020).

Accordingly, Afolayan (2011) in Ikwuegbu (2017, p.226) affirmed that, "widowhood deprives women of homes, comforts, agricultural lands and other valuables." Without inheritance rights widows are practically dependent on occasional charity of their husband's friends.

Psychological and Health challenges: Psychologically, widows are thrown into serious mental stress at the death of their spouses. The inhuman treatment faced during the period of mourning and after lingers and can lead to other complications.

Sickness is another major threat to the peace of the widow. With her low income and status, she finds it very difficult to rise to her challenges when sickness strikes in the family. According to Damap (2007), "most of the illnesses found within the household of many widows are nutrition-related; they eat whatever is available only to fill up their stomach." Most of these widows do not have good means of livelihood, some do not eat well.

Widowhood and Care in Biblical Perspectives

The Bible is replete with stories about and commands concerning widows (Bloechl, 2022). God cares for widows and calls His people to do the same in both Old and New Testaments of the Bible. God assumed the responsibility of taking care of the widows that lost their bread winners. The Psalmist describes God as the protector and upholder of widows (Ps. 68:5, 146:9). It is evident that care of widows is a priority in God's economy. The biblical widows like Ruth, the widow of Zarephat, the widow of Nain and Dorcas were taken care of by God (Nwaudo,

2012). He did not only care for the widows but also, He defended their cause (Exodus 22:22-24). The Israelites were warned not to persecute and exploit the widows (Kunhiyop, 2008). Widows were not abandoned in the New Testament. The early Christians quickly responded to the murmurings of the Grecians that complained that their widows were neglected in the sharing of food which led the church to appoint the seven deacons (Acts 6:1). But, the apostolic dispensation witnessed a tremendous decline in the caring of widows. In that era, heads of families, *pater familias*, declined in providing for the widows in their families. This situation prompted Paul to write a letter to Timothy admonishing Christian men that any man who fails to take care of the widow in his family has denied the faith (1 Timothy 5:8) (Pfeiffer, Vos and Rea, 2000). The church filled the gap created by families by providing relief for the elderly widows that had no relations that would take care of them (James 1:27, 1 Timothy 5:9) (Strong, 1999). The relief contributed a lot in alleviating the plight of widows in the New Testament period.

The Pastoral Care Approaches to Widowhood Challenges in Igbo Land

The contributions of pastoral counsellors and church leaders in general, in ameliorating the plight of widows in Igbo land cannot be overemphasized. These range from spiritual, psychological, material, advocacy and humanitarian assistance.

Spiritual and Psychological support: The first approach of pastoral counsellors towards widows generally, is to encourage, restore hope and disabuse their psychological disposition of thinking that all hope is lost, with the death of their husbands. Widows at this point in life need all the spiritual assistance like prayers and word of assurance from the counsellors. This in turn will heal them psychologically.

Pastoral Advocacy: The widows are greatly disadvantaged in Igbo land and need to be taken care of by the laws of the land; their voices heard and their needs addressed. Widows in traditional cultures are voiceless in most cases. It is the roles of Pastors and Church leaders to speak against cultures and traditions in Igbo land that still dehumanize, traumatize, abuse, relegate and mistreat widows. Widows are humans and must be treated as such. Iwe (2000) responding to the plight of widows and widowhood practices today averred that personality is perceived as the foundation of man's dignity and sense of responsibility. This should distinguish man from the other creatures of the universe; hence man (generic) should not be treated as an inanimate object.

Educational and Material support: Pastors should encourage the girl-child education so as to mitigate the worrisome effects of early child marriage that critically endangers the future of the young woman. Skills acquisition centers can be established where majority of these widows can easily learn one trade or the other so as to meet their daily needs.

The church must also stand with the widow if her late husband's family come to lay claim to his property. The church, and especially the pastor, should intervene to mediate between the parties and restrain abuses (Kunhiyop, 2008).

Humanitarian assistance: The church has founded humanitarian associations to cater for the needs of widows. There are associations of widows in many Christian denominations in Igbo land. These associations are saddled with the responsibility of alleviating the plight of widows. In many occasions, widows smile homes with money, cloths and food stuffs. The children of indigent widows are offered scholarships. Onah (2008, p.77) observed that the church through women organization has reduced the burden of widowhood. The church has reduced the mourning period from one year to six months while few widows do not observe

widowhood rites. Some widows can now take baths and sit on upholstery chairs. The mourning cloth has changed from black to white which symbolizes purity and innocence (Obi and Ogbenna, 2010).

Conclusion

This paper has reinforced the invaluable contributions of Pastoral counselling and care in handling the challenges of widows in traditional Igbo society. Widowhood rites in Igbo land has dehumanized and degraded widows. Widows pass through excruciating pains like loss of breadwinners, companions and heads of families. However, instead of being comforted and given succor, she is being subjected to further sorrow and anguish. It is based on this, that the pastoral counsellors should intervene as the last hope of widows in order to alleviate her plight. On that note, the following recommendations have been adduced to mitigate the pains of widows in Igbo land.

Recommendations

1. The church should not stop at reducing the period of mourning, changing the colour of mourning cloth, but also should address the remote causes of widowhood rites in order to abolish this ugly practice that is contrary to reason as well as unacceptable in the 21st century.
2. The church should contribute relief for the indigent widows to enable them take care of their families.
3. Pastors should intensify pastoral care by visiting and counseling the widows to enable them overcome psychological problems like fear, loneliness and anger.
4. There should be workshops, seminars and symposia for widows, where they will be sensitized on how to live as Christian widows.
5. Pastors should campaign against and work with policy makers to abolish widowhood rites in Igbo land generally.

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